

Fabrication and Thermal Lamination of Electrospun Polyamide 6 (PA6) Nanofibrous Composite Membranes

Fatma Yalcinkaya

Institute for Nanomaterials, Advanced Technologies and Innovation, Technical University of Liberec, Studentská 1402/2, 461 17 Liberec, Czech Republic

fatma.yalcinkaya@tul.cz

Aim and Objective:

The primary aim of this study is to fabricate electrospun Polyamide 6 (PA6) nanofibrous membranes and develop multilayer composite structures through thermal lamination. The objective is to investigate the effect of different lamination temperatures on the structural integration of PA6 nanofibers with supporting layers, while maintaining consistent pressure and nanofiber density. This process targets the production of mechanically stable, thermally bonded nanofibrous membranes suitable for potential applications in filtration, protective textiles, or composite reinforcement.

Preparation of Electrospun Polyamide 6 (PA6) Nanofibers:

Electrospun PA6 nanofibers were fabricated using a Nanospider NS 1WS500U (Elmarco s.r.o., Czech Republic) as shown in Figure 1. A 12% (w/v) PA6 polymer solution was prepared by dissolving the polymer in a 2:1 mixture of acetic acid and formic acid. The electrospinning process was conducted under controlled conditions with ambient humidity maintained at 35% RH and temperature at 23 °C. The electrode distance was set at 180 mm and a total voltage of 65 kV was applied. The resulting nanofiber web was deposited with a target areal density of 1.5 g/m² and an approximate thickness of 20 μm.

Figure 1. Nanospider NS 1WS500U electrospinning device.

Preparation of Nanofibrous Composite Membranes:

To fabricate composite membranes, the PA6 nanofiber mats were cut into A4-sized sheets (210 × 297 mm²). These nanofiber layers were laminated onto a 120 g/m² polyethylene terephthalate (PET) nonwoven support using a 12 g/m² adhesive web. Lamination was carried out using a heat-press machine equipped with two metallic plates (upper and lower). The assembly configuration included the PA6 nanofiber on top, the

adhesive web in the middle, and the PET spunbond nonwoven at the bottom. Two protective silicone sheets were placed above and below the multilayer stack to prevent direct contact with the heated plates (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Heat-press lamination device.

Thermal lamination was performed at three different temperatures—110 °C, 125 °C, and 135 °C—for a total duration of three minutes per sample. Pressure was applied in two stages: 30 kN for the first two minutes and 50 kN for the final minute. This lamination protocol was kept constant for all samples. The multilayer nanofibrous membranes were labeled according to the nanofiber material, areal density, and applied lamination temperature, for example: PA6-1.5-110, PA6-1.5-125, and PA6-1.5-135. Here, “PA6-1.5-110” indicates a PA6 nanofiber layer with 1.5 g/m² areal density laminated at 110 °C. Since the applied pressure remained constant, it was excluded from the sample naming convention.

Results

Table 1 indicates the PA6 nanofiber and their GSM, type of adhesive, type of supporting layer and, abbreviation of membranes and their lamination conditions.

Table 1. Nanofiber membranes and their abbreviations for Polyamide 6

Type(s) of polymeric nanofiber	GSM	Temperature(°C) used to prepare samples	Type of supporting layer	Preparation condition of Samples (lamination Condition)	Fiber diameter (nm)	Abbreviation of sample(s)
Polyamide 6	1.5	110	PET	2 minutes 30 KN pressure and 1 minute 50 KN pressure with 110 ⁰ C temperature.	90±19	PA6-1.5-110
		125		2 minutes 30 KN pressure and 1 minute 50 KN pressure with 125 ⁰ C temperature.	114±22	PA6-1.5-125
		135		2 minutes 30 KN pressure and 1 minute 50 KN pressure with 135 ⁰ C temperature.	113±19	PA6-1.5-135

Air Permeability, pore size and water permeability tests are done and results are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. PA6 samples name with pore size and air permeability, water permeability(flux) and contact angle.

Name of Samples	Pore size (μm)	Average Air permeability ($\text{l/m}^2/\text{s}$)	DI Water permeability ($\text{L}/(\text{m}^2\text{hbar})$)	Avr. WCA ($^\circ$)	Image
PA6-1.5-110	0.3398	5.6	14737.20	83.5 \pm 2.5	
PA6-1.5-125	0.4224	4.8	8450.020	83 \pm 3.2	
PA6-1.5-135	0.5513	3.5	9211.613	80.45 \pm 3.7	

The effect of lamination temperature on the structural and functional properties of PA6 nanofibrous membranes is clearly reflected in the results presented in Tables 1 and 2. As the lamination temperature increased from 110 $^\circ\text{C}$ to 135 $^\circ\text{C}$, a notable change was observed in fiber morphology and performance characteristics. The fiber diameter increased slightly from 90 ± 19 nm at 110 $^\circ\text{C}$ to 114 ± 22 nm at 125 $^\circ\text{C}$, remaining nearly constant thereafter at 113 ± 19 nm at 135 $^\circ\text{C}$. This increase in diameter is likely due to fiber coalescence or partial melting at higher temperatures, contributing to the observed changes in pore size and membrane permeability. The pore size followed an upward trend, increasing from 0.3398 μm in PA6-1.5-110 to 0.5513 μm in PA6-1.5-135, indicating that higher temperatures may cause pore enlargement or structural loosening of the nanofiber web due to thermal softening and adhesive flow.

Correspondingly, both air permeability and water flux showed temperature-dependent behavior. The sample laminated at the lowest temperature (PA6-1.5-110) exhibited the highest air permeability (5.6 $\text{l/m}^2/\text{s}$) and water flux (14,737.2 $\text{L}/\text{m}^2\text{h}\cdot\text{bar}$), correlating with its smallest fiber diameter and pore size, which suggests a more open and porous structure without significant adhesive blockage. In contrast, PA6-1.5-125 and PA6-1.5-135 showed decreased air permeability and water flux, likely due to increased pore deformation or partial fusion of fibers that reduced the membrane's openness. Furthermore, the water contact angle (WCA) slightly decreased with rising temperature, from 83.5 $^\circ$ at 110 $^\circ\text{C}$ to 80.45 $^\circ$ at 135 $^\circ\text{C}$, which may indicate marginal changes in surface energy or roughness due to thermal effects. Overall, the lamination temperature plays a critical role in tuning the membrane structure and transport properties, with lower temperatures favoring higher permeability and hydrophilicity, while higher temperatures enhance mechanical integration at the cost of reduced permeability.

Conclusion

This study successfully demonstrated the fabrication and thermal lamination of electrospun PA6 nanofibrous membranes using varying lamination temperatures (110 $^\circ\text{C}$, 125 $^\circ\text{C}$, and 135 $^\circ\text{C}$) under controlled pressure conditions. The results show that lamination temperature significantly influences the structural integrity and functional performance of the membranes. Lower temperature lamination (PA6-1.5-110) preserved finer fiber diameters, smaller pore sizes, and resulted in superior air and water permeability, making it more suitable for applications requiring high breathability and filtration efficiency. Conversely,

higher temperatures led to increased fiber diameter and pore size, along with reduced permeability, likely due to thermal fusion and densification effects. These findings highlight the importance of optimizing lamination parameters to tailor nanofibrous membrane properties for specific end-use applications.

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